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ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF CLOVE ESSENTIAL OIL (*SYZYGIVM AROMATICUM*) AGAINST STRAINS OF *ESCHERICHIA COLI*, *PSEUDOMONAS AERUGINOSA*, AND *SALMONELLA* SSP

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Clove (*Syzygium aromaticum*), a member of the Myrtaceae family, is cultivated in various regions of Asia, Africa, and the West. Its primary compound, eugenol, imparts a distinctive aroma and flavor while exhibiting bactericidal properties. **Objective:** This study evaluated the antibacterial activity of clove essential oil against *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Salmonella spp.*, isolated from food and water. **Methods:** The essential oil was extracted from dried flower buds using hydrodistillation with a Clevenger apparatus. The antimicrobial activity of the oil and the susceptibility of the strains to commercial antibiotics were assessed using the disk diffusion method. **Results and Discussion:** The essential oil from *Syzygium aromaticum* demonstrated high antibacterial activity against two of the three tested strains (*Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella spp.*) while exhibiting moderate efficacy against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. **Conclusions:** The microbiological study revealed that clove essential oil possesses significant antibacterial activity against the tested strains, with eugenol being the primary contributor to this effectiveness.

Keywords: Essential Oil. *Syzygium Aromaticum*. Clove. Eugenol. Antibacterial Activity

1. INTRODUCTION

The Clove (*Syzygium aromaticum*), part of the *Myrtaceae* family, is cultivated in various regions of Asia, Africa, and South America (Ferrão, 1993). The dried flower buds, known as cloves, are highly valued in cooking for their intense aroma and distinctive flavor, primarily due to eugenol, a phenolic compound that accounts for up to 95% of the oil extracted from the leaves (Gomes *et al.*, 2018; Raina *et al.*, 2001). Eugenol is also widely used in dentistry, serving as a key component in sealants and oral antiseptics, demonstrating significant bactericidal activity (Chong *et al.*, 1997; Kaplan *et al.*, 1999; Shapiro *et al.*, 1994). The growing demand for essential oils from cloves has driven research into their extraction and commercial applications (Clifford *et*

al., 1999; Rovio *et al.*, 1999).

Additionally, eugenol is a precursor in the synthesis of other phenolic compounds and is investigated in toxicological studies (Priefert *et al.*, 2001). Therefore, this study aims to evaluate the antibacterial activity of the essential oil extracted from the dried flower buds of Clove (*Syzygium aromaticum*) against strains of *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Salmonella spp.*

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted at the Laboratory of Analytical Chemistry Research (LPQA) of the Analytical Center, as well as at the Physical Chemistry and Microbiology Laboratory of the Technological Pavilion at the Federal

University of Maranhão (UFMA) and at the Analytical Center of the State University of Campinas (Unicamp-SP).

2.1. Materials

The reagents used in this study were of analytical grade: Müller Hinton Agar (500 g, Himedia), BHI Agar (500 g, Himedia), and eugenol standard (99%, Sigma).

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Collection of Clove Fruits

The clove fruits used in this research were sourced from the informal market associated with the Reviver project in São Luís. The selected material was placed in sealed plastic bags and stored in a dry, ventilated area. The dried flower buds were ground using a mill, and the resulting material was stored in a polyethylene container for subsequent essential oil extraction.

2.2.2. Extraction, Treatment, and Storage of Essential Oil

For the extraction of essential oil from *Syzygium aromaticum*, a Clevenger extractor was employed, connected to a 1000 mL round-bottom flask and a heating mantle. Approximately 69 grams of dried clove flower buds were combined with 200 mL of distilled water. The heating mantle was activated to maintain a constant temperature of 100°C. After 5 hours, the distillation process was completed, and the essential oil was collected. To dry the oil, anhydrous sodium sulfate was used for percolation. These procedures were performed in triplicate, and the samples were stored in glass containers under refrigeration to minimize potential loss of volatile components (Gomes *et al.*, 2019).

2.2.3. Antibacterial Activity Testing

The strains of *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella spp.*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* utilized in this study were obtained from food samples provided by the Microbiology Laboratory of the Food and Water Quality Control Program (PCQA) at the Federal University of Maranhão. The antibacterial activity of the essential oil and eugenol standard was assessed using the disk diffusion method as recommended by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (2005 (Novacosk and Torres, 2006)). Bacterial cultures were inoculated into BHI broth (Brain and Heart Infusion) and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Subsequently, dilutions were made to obtain a standardized suspension

corresponding to a 0.5 McFarland standard (10⁸ microorganisms/mL). A 0.1 mL inoculum from each bacterial culture was swabbed onto the surface of Mueller Hinton Agar plates. Small filter paper discs (6 mm in diameter), each impregnated with 75 µL of the essential oil and the eugenol standard, were gently pressed onto the agar surface. The plates were then incubated at 37°C for 24 hours, and the inhibition zones were measured using a calibrated ruler certified by INMETRO (National Institute of Metrology, Quality and Technology).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The antibacterial activity of clove essential oil *Syzygium aromaticum* was analyzed using the disk diffusion method, involving strains of *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella spp.*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, as illustrated in Table 1. The strains of *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella*, isolated from food, showed sensitivity to the essential oil, with inhibition halos of 16 mm and 18 mm, respectively. In contrast, the *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* strains, isolated from water, did not respond to the essential oil.

The positive results of both clove oil and the standard eugenol align with previous studies. (Novacosk and Torres, 2006) identified that among five essential oils extracted from medicinal plants, those exhibiting the highest antimicrobial activity were rich in alcohols, phenols, and aldehydes. Additionally, (Asolini *et al.*, 2006) reported antimicrobial activity in all phenolic compounds extracted from ten plants used in teas. According to (Alzoreky and Nakahara, 2003) inhibition halos smaller than 12 mm are not indicative of antibacterial activity. However, for essential oils containing eugenol as the main component, their efficacy as antibacterial agents is recognized when the inhibition halo reaches between 8 mm and 10 mm, as demonstrated by (Cimanga *et al.*, 2002; Farago *et al.*, 2004; Moreira *et al.*, 2005).

It is important to consider that the diffusion rate of substances in agar can influence the zone of inhibition of bacterial growth. The essential oil, due to its viscosity and low polarity, may have its diffusion impeded. Therefore, any halo obtained, even if small, suggests the presence of antibacterial activity in the oil, as indicated by (Fonseca *et al.*, 2006; Glisic *et al.*, 2007).

The results concerning the antibacterial activity of clove essential oil and the standard eugenol against the strains of *E. coli* and the strain isolated from lettuce revealed inhibition halos

considered sensitive. (Matan *et al.*, 2006) highlight that the active compounds present in oils rich in eugenol and other aldehydes can interfere with the synthesis of bacterial enzymes and damage the structure of bacterial cell walls. Essential oils containing eugenol, such as cinnamon oil, also demonstrated comparable inhibitory potential against *E. coli* strains. Although specific photochemical analysis of the studied oils was not conducted, the presence of active compounds and eugenol as the principal component likely contributed to the significant antibacterial activity observed (Scherer *et al.*, 2009; Silvestri *et al.*, 2010).

Clove essential oil and its principal component, eugenol, demonstrated antimicrobial activity against the gram-negative strains *Salmonella spp.* and *Salmonella* isolated from sururu (*Mytella guyanensis*). The inhibition halos measured were 15 mm for both the oil and eugenol. Notably, when tested against *Salmonella* isolated from food (sururu), an even greater inhibition was observed, with a value of 18 mm.

According to Cimanga *et al.* (2002), essential oils that yield inhibition halos below 10 mm are considered inactive, while those between 10 mm and 15 mm are classified as active. In the case of the essential oil from the dried flower buds of *Syzygium aromaticum*, excellent antibacterial activity was observed for two of the three tested strains (*Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella spp.*), with inhibition halos equal to or exceeding 15 mm. For the **Pseudomonas aeruginosa** strains, the oil showed a halo of 12 mm, classified as moderately active.

The mechanism by which essential oils combat bacteria is not yet fully understood. Studies suggest that their action begins at the cell membrane due to the lipophilic and volatile properties of these oils (Stammati *et al.*, 1999). (Burt, 2004) emphasizes that the synergistic interaction of the oil's components is what makes it effective as an antibacterial agent. This synergy justifies the activity of the essential oil against the tested bacteria, and the efficiency gain is attributed to the other components of the oil.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The essential oil of *Syzygium aromaticum* (clove) demonstrated significant antibacterial activity against two of the three tested strains, specifically *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella spp.* At the same time, it showed moderate activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. These results suggest that clove may serve as a natural and

cost-effective alternative for food preservation, as well as being effective in combating certain diseases.

5. DECLARATIONS

5.1. Open Access

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Table 1. Sensitivity of *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella spp.*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* strains to the essential oil of *Syzygium aromaticum* and the standard eugenol, using the disk diffusion method. Source: the author.

Components	<i>E.coli</i> (mm)		<i>Salmonella spp</i> (mm)		<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> (mm)	
	Standard	Lettuce	Standard	<i>Mytella guyane nsis</i>	Standard	Water
Essential oil	16	16	15	18	12	-
Eugenol	19	16	15	18	12	12